

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF KAHOOT APPLICATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article dedicated to implementing Kahoot application in ELT classroom in order to create an alternative learning strategy. During the research it is proven the effectiveness of using video as a learning medium for students. Using Kahoot application does not only give pleasure for students to be more active and comfortable in learning process. Apart from this, teacher knows how to deliver excellent material by utilizing Kahoot online application. All in all, Kahoot is considered to be one strategy that makes students to enjoy learning and teaching process.

Key words: Alternative Learning Strategy, Kahoot application, App, English Language Teaching, phenomena, education institutions.

The main goal of teaching English is to help students' sub-skills which are reading, listening, writing and speaking. It helps them to communicate with a sufficient level while studying abroad or working in the future. Balla (2017) pointed out that learners are taught in schools which means that it is vital not only academically but also in practical aspects of learning. They can utilize the language different purposes such as business goals, communicating with somebody, reading foreign literature and other types. Hamuddin (2017) noted that there are a wide range of factors which show us to understand English instruction is important in using and communication around the world. Muhammad (2018) cited that English is considered to be as a function for interaction and communication tools in a classroom. Nowadays, the majority of teachers tend to implement strategies or technological tools in order to teach English naturally and straightforward. It means that learners

are drawn their attention for the lesson. The development of existing science and technology plays a great role in teaching not only the language but also any sphere.

It can be clearly seen that there are a wide range of reasons why the quality of education is becoming lower and lower from day to day. Firstly, using of inappropriate method causes learners to be bored with the lesson. Secondly, the inadequate technological or evaluation tool which does not provide with the level of thinking learners. If teachers tend to use appropriate learning media, it impacts learning process positively and increases student’s learning achievement.

According to differentiated method, neither a single group is the best nor a single media is suitable for all types of learning material. For this reason, professional teacher should master different media and methods to use and can choose which media is appropriate for use in a specific group.

Buckingham (2007) noted that as a teacher learning media is a vital dimension of technology in education. It helps learners to learn new digital and get experiences of technological tools outside of school and show their experiences for other learners in a classroom. The study takes into consideration three ways in which utilizing media can respond to new digital media, by applying and extending existing conceptual approaches to the objects of this new study, addressing the creative possibilities of digital technology, and the pedagogical challenges it represents and indicate the potential forms of participatory media culture that emerge. According to Ahmad (2012), regarding to the responses of EFL learners in media technology plays a huge role in enhancing learner’s accent patterns in individual English words and improving learner’s writing skills.

Hamuddin (2018) cited that in order to enhance learner’s motivation, integrate the language skills, self-study environment and create an English atmosphere, teachers should be able to add media technology in a classroom. Lee (2016) mentioned learners can be motivated and be interested in the digital literacy curriculum with the help of using new media technology. Additionally, learners can have an opportunity of using computers, laptops and iPads in order to discover and

discuss media problems in the classroom. Besides that, they achieve to improve their 4C skills including critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration.

Learning media should be connected with environmental conditions, subject matter, infrastructure and learning objectives. It is clear that using of suitable learning media helps to achieve learning objectives with the help of effectiveness and efficiency of the media. Additionally, the study illustrates the data about the implementation of application Kahoot in teaching English language. So far the majority of teachers applied different approaches, strategies, media and learning models to improve English learning. Jack Richards (2004) noted that Kahoot is considered to be an online game which helps to increase learners' intrinsic motivation. He explored that active learning, student involvement, self-efficacy, independent learning and a growth in the results of summative assessment were increased after using Kahoot application.

According to Medina (2017), Kahoot application is technological tool to teach and learn vocabulary in English classes. Next, the study illustrates an evidence that integrating Kahoot application in learning environment helps students to increase their vocabulary and encourage their motivation to the class. There is a marked satisfaction that EFL learners are interested in using Kahoot application in a classroom during the learning process and they can learn how to use easily. It can be clearly seen that learners have a positive view about Kahoot and are satisfied with using it during the lesson. According to Budiati (2017), while studying Kahoot, this application is designed as a combination of the use of ICT in education and games which is acceptable in English classroom to improve learners' learning process. There are a variety of functions that teachers and students can apply and use in different ways. Having integrated Kahoot application in learning process, learners are really keen on attending class, they are more eager to participate in the lesson, they are more attentive during the lesson. What is more, they tend to convey the data about Kahoot for other learners what they have learned from Kahoot. Bicen (2018) claimed that Kahoot application can play a role in gamification of lessons and impact learners to be more motivated than typical lessons. If teachers utilize Kahoot online media in

the learning process, they can develop the quality of student learning in the classroom, with the highest influences reporting on class dynamics, involvement, motivation, and improving learning experiences.

References:

1. Brown, D.H. (2001). Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy-2 nd Edition. New York: Longman.
2. Brown, S. (2006). Teaching Listening. Cambridge: Cambridge university press.
3. Harmer, Jeremy. (2003). The Practice of English Language Teaching. Third Edition. England: Pearson Education Limited.
4. Osada, Nobuko. (2004). Listening Comprehension Research: A brief Review of the Past Thirty Years. Dialogue, 2004, Vol. 3, pp 53-66, ISSN 1349-5135
5. Richards, J. (ed). (2005). Second Language Listening – Theory and Practice. Cambridge:Cambridge University Press.
6. Rubin, Joan. (1994). A review of Second Language Listening Comprehension Research. The Modern Language Journal, 78, ii (1994) 0026-7902/94/199-221
7. Thurnbury, Scot. (2009). How to teach speaking. London: Cambridge.
8. Projectlifemastery.com
9. learningenglish.voanews.com/a/babies-development-learning-child-care